

EFFECT OF AUGER RECOMBINATION ON THE EMITTER SATURATION CURRENT OF SI-DRIFT SOLAR CELLS

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Abstract:

The dark saturation current of drift-field solar cells is conventionally modeled by considering only SRH (Shockley-Read-Hall) recombination. Since heavy and nonuniform doping level is required to apply in these solar cells to improve the current-voltage characteristics, Auger recombination becomes significant and hence, should be included in the modeling. However, simultaneous consideration of both SRH and Auger recombination mechanisms results in an intractable analytical modeling. In this work, resolving this intractability problem by using an elegant exponential approximation technique, an analytical model for the dark saturation current in the heavily and non-uniformly doped emitter region of silicon drift-field solar cell has been developed. The simulation results of the developed model shows the significance of Auger recombination even for a very thin (≤ 100 nm) emitter when surface recombination velocity is lowered to the order of 10^4 cm/s and/or when the doping level is of the order of 10^{20} cm⁻³.

Key words: Auger Recombination, SRH Recombination, Emitter Dark Saturation Current, Doping Dependent Mobility, Doping Dependent Lifetime.

I. INTRODUCTION

The conversion efficiency of a solar cell strongly depends on the fill factor and hence, on the shape of the current-voltage characteristics. In a solar cell, the load voltage forward-biases the p-n junction which results in a diode current in the direction opposite to that of the photo-generated current. As a result, the load current drastically decreases with the increase of the load voltage. This diode action worsens the shape of the current voltage characteristics and hence, reduces the fill factor as well as the conversion efficiency. The detrimental diode action can be reduced by reducing its reverse saturation current (for solar cells, which is commonly termed as the dark saturation current). Introducing electric fields in the bulk regions (i.e. emitter and base regions) in the same direction as that of the built-in field developed in the depletion region can reduce the diode current and hence, improve the conversion efficiency. These fields can be developed in

the emitter and base regions by introducing non-uniform doping profiles instead of commonly used uniform doping profiles. This is the concept of a drift-field (DF) solar cell [1]. Therefore, the DF solar cells have higher conversion efficiency than the conventional solar cells.

The conversion efficiency of the DF solar cells can be made higher by increasing the strength of the electric fields developed in the bulk regions. This increase in the field can be achieved, if the peak doping level in the bulk regions can be made higher. However, use of increasingly heavy doping levels results in the dominance of the Auger recombination as well as invokes several non-ideal effects which include the band-gap narrowing effect and the doping dependency of the carrier transport parameters (i.e. mobility and lifetime). Moreover, due to the non-uniformity of the doping level, the transport parameters becomes position-dependent. Therefore, inclusion of all these effects makes the analytical modeling of the DF solar cells with high conversion efficiency intractable.

Till to date various researchers [2-7] have been working on the accurate modeling of dark saturation current considering all the above-mentioned non-ideal effects. Bullis [2] developed an analytical model for dark saturation current assuming uniform mobility. Kaye et al. [3] and Overstraeten et al. [4] considered position dependence of carrier mobility; but they assumed this dependence as linear. Lindholm & Chen [5] developed an analytical model by incorporating doping dependent carrier lifetime; but they neglected the doping dependency of the carrier mobility. Verhoff and Sinke [6] considered the doping dependence of both carrier mobility and lifetime. But, for lifetime, they considered the SRH and Auger recombination separately, not simultaneously; they considered Auger recombination for doping level $\geq 5 \times 10^{18}$ cm⁻³ and SRH recombination for lower doping levels.

In this work, the problem of mathematical intractability due to simultaneous consideration of SRH and Auger recombination has been properly addressed and has been resolved by applying an elegant exponential approximation technique. The analytical model developed in this work also considered all the non-ideal effects mentioned earlier in this section. Finally, simulations are carried over using the developed model

to investigate the effect of simultaneous consideration of both SRH and Auger recombination.

II. Analysis

The basic equations required for the n-type emitter region of a drift solar cell are

$$J_p = qp(x)\mu_p(x)E(x) - qD_p(x)\frac{dp(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -q(R_p - G_p) \quad (2)$$

where μ_p and D_p are the mobility and the diffusivity of hole, $R_p - G_p$ is the net recombination rate and $E(x)$ is the electric field acting on the hole caused by the nonuniform doping profile. Considering the bandgap narrowing (BGN) effects due to heavy doping level, the electric field $E(x)$ can be expressed as [8]

$$\frac{E}{V_T} = -\frac{d}{dx} \ln N_d(x) + \frac{d}{dx} \ln n_{ie}^2(x) \quad (3)$$

where n_{ie} is the effective intrinsic carrier concentration due to BGN effects given by [9]

$$n_{ie}^2(x) = n_{i0}^2 \left[\frac{N_d(x)}{N_{0,ref}} \right]^{\gamma_2} \quad (4)$$

Where $n_{i0} = 1.194 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_{0,ref} = 1.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.5355$. For practical doping density ranges, hole mobility μ_p becomes doping dependent. This doping dependency can be approximated as [6]

$$\mu_p = \frac{qD_p(0)}{kT} \left[\frac{N_d(x)}{N_{ref}} \right]^{-\gamma_3} \quad (5)$$

with $D_p(0) = 12.57 \text{ cm}^2 (\text{V.s})^{-1}$, $\gamma_3 = 0.38$ and $N_{ref} = 1.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For a heavily doped silicon,

the band-to-band Auger recombination involving direct transitions and SRH recombination through traps are significant. Under steady-state condition, these recombination rates are given by

$$R_{SRH} = \frac{P}{\tau_{ps}} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{Auger} = \frac{P}{\tau_{pa}} \quad (7)$$

where τ_{ps}, τ_{pa} are the doping dependent carrier lifetime for SRH recombination and for Auger recombination, respectively and can be expressed as

$$\tau_{ps} = \frac{\tau_{p0}}{1 + \frac{N_d}{N_{0,ref}}} \quad [10] \quad (8)$$

$$\tau_{pa} = \frac{1}{C_{An} N_d^2} \quad (9)$$

where $N_{0,ref} = 7.1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ sec}$ and

$\tau_{p0} = 3.52 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}$ [11] and C_{An} is the Auger coefficient for holes given by [12]

$$C_{An} = 0.67 \times 10^{-31} + 8.16 \times 10^{-34} T - 2.44 \times 10^{-37} T^2$$

The total recombination rate R_p in the emitter region can be expressed as

$$R_p = \frac{P}{\tau_{p,eff}} \quad (10)$$

where $\tau_{p,eff}$ is the effective hole lifetime given by

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{p,eff}} = \frac{\tau_{p0}}{1 + \frac{N_d}{N_{0,ref}}} + C_{An} N_d^2 \quad (11)$$

Since this work considers the dark condition, the generation rate G_p is zero. Therefore, the hole current continuity equation given by Eqn. (2) can be rearranged as

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -\frac{qP}{\tau_{p,eff}} \quad (12)$$

A. Model Derivation

Differentiating Eqn. (1) with respect to x, combining with Eqn. (12) and then rearranging, results in a second order differential equation (DE) of p(x) as

$$\frac{d^2 p}{dx^2} + \left[-\frac{E}{V_T} - \frac{d}{dx} \ln \left(\frac{1}{qD_p} \right) \right] \frac{dp}{dx} + \left[-\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{E}{V_T} \right) + \frac{E}{V_T} \frac{d}{dx} \ln \left(\frac{1}{qD_p} \right) - \frac{1}{\tau_{p,eff} D_p} \right] p = 0 \quad (13)$$

Since the electric field, mobility and lifetime- all depend on the type of the doping profile, the solution of the above-mentioned DE can be obtained, provided that the doping profile in the emitter region is specified. In this work, the emitter doping profile is considered as exponential which can be expressed as

$$N_d(x) = N_d(0)u(x) = N_d(0)e^{-\frac{nx}{W_E}} \quad (14)$$

where u is a convenient variable,

$\eta = \log \left[\frac{N_d(0)}{N_d(W_E)} \right]$ is the logarithmic slope of the doping profile and $N_d(0)$ and $N_d(W_E)$ are the doping densities at $x=0$ and $x=W_E$ i.e. at the surface of the emitter and at the edge of the junction.

For the exponential profile, the electric field, the carrier mobility and the lifetimes for SRH and Auger recombination can be arranged as

$$\frac{E}{V_T} = \frac{\eta}{W_E} (1 - \gamma_2) \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{1}{qD_p} = \frac{1}{qD_p(0)} \left[\frac{N_d(0)}{N_{0ref}} \right]^{\gamma_3} u^{\gamma_3} = F_h u^{\gamma_3} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{ps}} \approx \frac{1}{\tau_{p0}} \frac{N_d(0)}{N_{0ref}} u = R_{ps} u \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{pa}} = C_{An} [N_d(0)]^2 u^2 = R_{pa} u^2 \quad (18)$$

Therefore, the DE [Eqn. 13] for the exponential doping profile can be organized as

$$\frac{d^2 p}{dx^2} + G_1 \frac{dp}{dx} + G_2 p = 0 \quad (19)$$

where

$$G_1 = -\frac{\eta}{W_E} (1 - \gamma_2 - \gamma_3)$$

$$G_2 = -\left[\left(\frac{\eta}{W_E} \right)^2 \gamma_3 (1 - \gamma_2) + F_h (R_{ps} u + R_{pa} u^2) u^{\gamma_3} \right]$$

The analytical intractability of this DE is due to the second term of G_2 . Therefore, Verhoff and Sinke [6] solved this DE by separately considering the SRH and Auger recombination i.e. they used either $R_{ps} u$ or $R_{pa} u^2$. In this work, using the exponential approximation technique [described in Appendix I], the

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{p,eff} D_p}$$

term can be approximated as a simple exponential given by

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{p,eff} D_p} \equiv R_0 u^k \quad (20)$$

where R_0 and k can be obtained using the relation given in Appendix 5. The solution of the DE [Eqn. 19] i.e. minority hole concentration $p(x)$ can be expressed

as a combination of modified Bessel functions of first and second kind of order β [I_β and K_β] as [Appendix II]

$$p(x) = w(x) [C_1 y_1(x) + C_2 y_2(x)] \quad (21)$$

where all variables and constants are defined in the

Appendix 6. The hole current density $J_p(x)$ in the emitter region can be obtained from the hole current

equation [Eqn. (1)] and taking the value of J_p at $x = W_E$ gives

$$J_p(W_E) = J_0 e^{\frac{qV_L}{KT}} \quad (22)$$

where J_0 is the emitter dark saturation current [6] given by

$$J_0 = \frac{qD_{pw} p_w}{\alpha_0} [\beta + X_w r_w] \quad (23)$$

where $\beta = \frac{1 - \gamma_2 + \gamma_3}{k_p}$, $\alpha_0 = \frac{2W_E}{\eta K_p}$ and subscript 'w' denotes the value at $x = W_E$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the simulation results to demonstrate the effects of Auger recombination on the

emitter dark saturation current density (J_0). The simulations are carried under three conditions such as

different surface recombination velocity (S_p), emitter width (W_E) and peak doping level ($N_d(0)$) to show whether and to which extent the effect of Auger recombination becomes significant.

Volume recombination in the Si-emitter region includes both SRH and Auger recombination mechanisms. Since heavy doping levels (commonly $> 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) are used in the emitter region, Auger recombination is more probable than the SRH recombination. Moreover, since

the dark saturation current J_0 needs to make up the carrier loss caused by the volume recombination in the

emitter region, J_0 has to be higher when considering both SRH and Auger recombination than that considering only the SRH or the Auger recombination

and also, J_0 considering only Auger recombination is higher than that considering only SRH recombination. It is evident that Figs. (1), (2) and (3) are in accordance with the above-mentioned statements.

Since the surface recombination velocity S_p represents the amount of surface defects at the edge of the emitter side of the solar cells, increase in S_p means increase in the defects and hence, increased carrier losses at the emitter surface. In order to make up this carrier losses at the surface, the dark saturation current J_0 has to increase. This fact is evidenced from the Figs. (1) and (2).

Figure 1: Effect of the variation of surface recombination velocity on the emitter saturation current density J_0 for two values of emitter width ($W_E = 100 \text{ nm}$ and 200 nm). Here, $N_d(0) = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 2: Effect of the variation of emitter width on the emitter saturation current density J_0 for two values of surface recombination velocity ($S_p = 4 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$ and $5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$). Here, $N_d(0) = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 3: Effect of the variation of emitter width on the emitter saturation current density J_0 for two values of peak doping concentration ($N_d(0) = 9 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Here, $S_p = 2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/sec}$. The dark saturation current in the emitter region flows from its surface side to the junction side. Due to the volume recombination in the emitter region, the current at the junction side is decreased from the surface side. Increase in emitter width (W_E), therefore, results in more lowering of the current at the junction side. Since J_0 is conventionally calculated at the junction side, the increase of the emitter width causes J_0 to decrease. From Figs. (1), (2) and (3), this trend of J_0 against W_E is reflected.

When peak emitter doping level $N_d(0)$ is increased keeping $N_d(W_E)$ constant, the electric field in the emitter region is increased due to the increase in the logarithmic gradient of the doping profile. On the other hand, this increase in $N_d(0)$ results in the increase of carrier population throughout the emitter region which, in turn, decreases the carrier mobility according to a power law [Eqn. (5)]. Therefore, the decrease in the carrier mobility dominates over the increase in the electric field when $N_d(0)$ is increased keeping $N_d(W_E)$ constant and hence, under such condition, J_0 gets decreasing. Figure (3) also supports this fact.

A close observation of the Figs. (1), (2) and (3) reveals that the effect of considering both SRH and Auger recombination instead of considering only SRH recombination becomes significant when S_p is lowered, when emitter width is decreased and when peak emitter doping is increased. Figs. (4), (5) and (6) show the percentage difference or error introduced

between these two consideration under three different circumstances.

Fig. (4) shows the percentage error for varying S_p for three different values of W_E . From this figure, it has been observed that lowering of S_p causes the inclusion of Auger recombination in determining J_0 to be more significant. This is expected from the fact lowering of S_p reduces surface recombination thereby causing volume recombination, especially, the Auger recombination to be dominant for high emitter doping levels. Moreover, increase in the emitter width increases the dominance of the Auger recombination for which % error is increased. This fact is also observed from Fig. (4). For an emitter of 50 nm width and doped with $1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, lowering of S_p to $2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$ results in an error of approximately 13%. This observation is important since S_p causes a significant high-energy photon loss (i.e. $\approx 59\%$ [13]) and hence, S_p needs to be lowered to improve the conversion efficiency of modern solar cells.

Fig. (5) shows the percentage error under varying $N_d(0)$ for three different values of W_E . This figure shows that effect of Auger recombination becomes dominant with the increase in $N_d(0)$. For a 50 nm wide emitter and with $S_p = 2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$, $N_d(0)$ of as low as $6 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ can produce errors more than 10%. Such a doping level in the emitter region is very common for modern drift-field solar cells.

Fig. (6) shows that percentage error for varying $N_d(0)$ under three different S_p values for a 100 nm wide emitter. This figure shows the dominance of Auger recombination when S_p is lowered or when $N_d(0)$ is increased. From this figure it is seen that the error introduced for the consideration of Auger recombination becomes more than 10% for a higher $N_d(0) = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with higher $S_p = 5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$ and for a lower $N_d(0) = 6 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with lower $S_p = 3 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$.

Figure 4: % error in emitter saturation current density considering Auger recombination against the variation of surface recombination velocity for three values of emitter width ($W_E = 50 \text{ nm}$, 100 nm , and 200 nm).

Here, $N_d(0) = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 5: % error in emitter saturation current density considering Auger recombination against the variation of peak emitter doping level for three values of emitter width ($W_E = 50 \text{ nm}$, 100 nm , and 200 nm).

Here, $S_p = 2 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$.

Figure 6: % error in emitter saturation current density considering Auger recombination against the variation of peak emitter doping level for three values of surface recombination velocity

($S_p = 3 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$, $4 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$).

and $5 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$). Here, $W_E = 100 \text{ nm}$.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, the effects of Auger recombination on the emitter dark saturation current density have been investigated and analyzed by developing an analytical model considering both SRH and Auger recombination mechanisms. The analytical intractability of the developed model has been resolved by employing an elegant exponential approximation technique. Simulation results obtained from the model under various considerations leads to the following important observations:

- Effect of Auger recombination is dominant when surface recombination velocity is lowered to the order of 10^4 cm/s .
- When the peak emitter doping level is increased to the order of 10^{20} cm^{-3} , Auger recombination should be included in the modeling.
- Even for a very thin emitter (close to 50 nm), the effect of Auger recombination cannot be neglected, provided that the surface recombination velocity is lowered to $3 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$ or less with a peak doping level increased to $6 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ or higher.

These observations are very much important for modern drift solar cells, since these cells are required to design with thinner emitter with heavy doping level and also, with lowered surface recombination velocity for the considerable improvement in the cell performance and the cell efficiency. Moreover, using the developed model in this work, the physics of various effects on the dark saturation current is readily understandable.

Appendix I: Exponential Approximation Technique
Extending the idea suggested in the work [14], any exponential-like function $f(x)$ defined in the region $0 < x < W$ can be approximated by a simple exponential function such that

$$f(x) \equiv F_0 e^{\frac{\eta x}{W}} \quad (24)$$

where the logarithmic slope η can be obtained from the boundary values of $f(x)$ as

$$\eta = \log \left[\frac{f(W)}{f(0)} \right] \quad (25)$$

and F_0 can be obtained from the fact that the areas under the original curve and the approximated curve must be equal

$$F_0 = \frac{\eta \int_0^W f(x) dx}{e^{\eta} - 1} \quad (26)$$

The above-mentioned technique is termed in this work as "Exponential Approximation Technique". Applying this technique can significantly reduce the mathematical complexity without the loss of physical understanding.
Appendix II: Solution of the DE

Letting $p(x) = v(x)w(x)$ converts the the second order differential equation (19) to

$$\frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + \left[\frac{2}{w} \frac{dw}{dx} + G_1 \right] \frac{dv}{dx} + \frac{1}{w} \left[\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + G_1 \frac{dw}{dx} + G_2 w \right] v(x) = 0 \quad (27)$$

Letting $\frac{2}{w} \frac{dw}{dx} + G_1 = 0$, $w(x)$ can be obtained as

$$w(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{2} \int G_1(x) dx} = u^{-\frac{1-\gamma_2-\gamma_3}{2}} \quad (28)$$

Finally, letting $u^{k_p} = z^2$ transforms the Eqn (27) to a modified Bessel equation of order β as

$$\frac{d^2 v}{dX^2} + \frac{1}{X} \frac{dv}{dX} - \frac{1}{X^2} (X^2 + \beta^2) v = 0 \quad (29)$$

where $X = b_0 z$. The solution $p(x)$ can be expressed as

$$p(x) = w(x) [c_1 y_1(x) + c_2 y_2(x)] \quad (30)$$

where $y_1(x) = I_\beta(X)$ and $y_2(x) = K_\beta(X)$ are the modified Bessel function of the first kind and the

$$\beta = \frac{1-\gamma_2+\gamma_3}{k_p}$$

second kind, respectively and

Applying the required boundary conditions at $x=0$ i.e. at the surface and at $x=W_E$ i.e at the depletion edge given by [6]

$$J_p(0) = qS_p p(0)$$

$$p(W_E) = \frac{n_{ie}^2(W_E)}{N_d(W_E)} e^{\frac{qV_L}{kT}}$$

where V_L is the load voltage. C_1, C_2 can be obtained as

$$C_1 = \frac{P_w}{y_{1w} - \beta_s y_{2w}}$$

$$C_2 = -\beta_s C_1$$

$$\beta_s = \frac{A_0 y_{10} + dy_{10}}{A_0 y_{20} + dy_{20}}$$

where and subscripts '0' and 'w' denotes the values at $x=0$ and $x=W_E$.

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